

CEDA Annual Report 23-24

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Introduction

PHIL KERSHAW, HEAD OF CEDA

This has been an exceptional year of change across many aspects of what we do from the make-up of the team, the work with our stakeholders and major new projects. The Earth Observation DataHub is one such example. It is a first of its kind, the development of a national computing platform to foster the greater exploitation of Earth Observation data. Through the National Centre for Earth Observation, CEDA is leading the work collaborating with public sector partners and industry. Besides the Hub, JASMIN has received a huge boost this year for its computing infrastructure with a major investment in hardware which has enabled an expansion of its processing capacity by a factor of two.

We welcomed new members to our management team - Fede Moscato as Head of Earth Observation and Dave Poulter as Technical Manager. Both bring a wealth of experience from industry and work in the research community. It was also a major change for us with Ag Stephens embarking on a part-time Masters Course in Artificial Intelligence sponsored through the RAL Space department. Though we miss his many talents in the day-to-day running of CEDA, he is bringing valuable new skills back that will be an investment in the future for us in this rapidly developing field.

As ever we are grateful for the talent and energy our graduates bring to our work. The 3-month placements are an excellent way for them to grow their skills but at the same time grow our relationships with the National Centre for Atmospheric Science and our other stakeholders as well as other parts of our host organisation (Science and Technology Facilities Council). We have been excited to participate in the Continuous Improvement programme in RAL Space which amongst other things has led us to move home to a new open-plan office space. Though this could be overlooked as a routine development, it has had a radical positive impact on our ability to interact and collaborate together.

Collaboration and communication continue to be key threads running through our work, illustrated for example in the article about the communication of uncertainty in the context of climate change or our section on the EO DataHub. Our staff are experts when it comes to cross-disciplinary collaboration, frequently working across a multitude of projects, organisations and domains.

By bringing people together and closing gaps, we are often the catalyst for large-scale collaborative projects that span numerous institutions and push progress in environmental science.

Team discussion at the Centre
for Environmental Data Analysis
© National Centre for Atmospheric Science

About CEDA

The [Centre for Environmental Data Analysis](#) (CEDA) is based in the [Science and Technology Facilities Council](#) (STFC)'s [RAL Space department](#). CEDA operates data centres and delivers data infrastructure, primarily for the [Natural Environment Research Council](#) (NERC), and undertakes project work for a range of national and international funders. CEDA's mission is to provide data and information services for environmental science. This includes curation of scientifically important environmental data for the long term, and facilitation of the use of data by the environmental science community.

CEDA Archive

The [CEDA Archive](#) was established in 2005, as a merged entity incorporating two NERC designated data centres: the British Atmospheric Data Centre, and the NERC Earth Observation Data Centre. Since April 2018, the CEDA Archive has been a component part of the [NERC Environmental Data Service](#), which brings together the five NERC data centres into a single service commissioned by NERC as National Capability.

JASMIN

[JASMIN](#) is a data intensive supercomputer which is developed and operated by STFC on behalf of NERC. JASMIN provides flexible data analysis capabilities to a user base that spans the environmental science community and beyond. They benefit from high performance compute and a private cloud, co-located with petascale data storage. JASMIN also provides the infrastructure upon which the CEDA Archive and services are delivered.

Charlotte Pascoe inspects
JASMIN computer servers at
Rutherford Appleton Laboratory
© National Centre for
Atmospheric Science

Over
2.5 Petabytes
of data was
deposited into the
CEDA Archive
this year

The CEDA team

We have had several new staff members join CEDA in the last year. In August we welcomed Chaminuka Mbanje to the JASMIN support team and Suresh Balaji temporarily into project management. In September, Federica Moscato was appointed Head of Earth Observation and in February 2024 Dave Poulter joined as CEDA Technical Manager.

We have gained 2 new graduates on the STFC graduate scheme: Jesse Alexander (Scientific Programming and Outreach) and Ellie Fisher (Data Scientist). We have also had two Industrial Placement students join us for the academic year, Rory Jenns and Zach Warton.

We have also said goodbye to Project Manager Katie Cartmell and Software Engineer Jack Leland who have moved on to pastures new.

Meet the team

Adrian Hines
Director of JASMIN

Ag Stephens
Head of Partnerships

Alan Iwi
Senior Software Engineer

Alex Manning
Research Software Engineer / Operations Support for JASMIN

Alison Pamment
Training and Standards Specialist

Alison Waterfall
Senior Data Scientist: Earth Observation

Andrew Harwood
Infrastructure Manager

Chaminuka Mbanje
JASMIN Storage and User Support

Charlotte Pascoe
Senior Data Scientist: Models

Daniel Westwood
Graduate Software Engineer

Dave Poulter
Technical Manager

Diane Knappett
Senior Data Scientist: Earth Observation

Ed Williamson
Senior Data Scientist: Earth Observation

Ellie Fisher
Graduate Data Scientist

Emily Anderson
Graduate Environmental Data Scientist

Esther Conway
Senior Data Scientist:
Earth Observation

Fatima Chami
JASMIN User
Support

Federica Moscato
Head of Earth
Observation

Graham Parton
Data Management
Specialist

Hayley Gray
User Support and
Metadata Services
Operator

Jennifer Bulpett
Senior Project
Manager

Jesse Alexander
Scientific
Programming and
Outreach Graduate

Martin Juckes
Head of Atmospheric
Science and
Research and deputy
head of CEDA

Matt Jones
Senior DevOps
Engineer

Matt Pritchard
JASMIN Operations
Manager

Matthew Wild
Senior Data Scientist:
UKSSDC

Molly MacRae
Graduate
Environmental Data
Scientist

Neil Massey
Senior Software
Engineer

Nicola Farmer
Graduate Software
Engineer

Phil Kershaw
Head of CEDA

Poppy Townsend
Communications
Manager

Rhys Evans
Software Engineer

Sam Pepler
Head of Curation

Steve Donegan
Senior Data Scientist:
Earth Observation

Wendy Garland
Senior Data Scientist:
Aircraft

William Tucker
Senior DevOps
Engineer

Innovating our services

SAM PEPLER

The key to CEDA's continuing impact are the two main services we run for the Natural Environment Research Council (NERC): the CEDA Archive and JASMIN. This section highlights some of the improvements and innovations that are essential to sustaining and enhancing our impact.

One of the critical changes this year is the appointment of an Integration and Engagement Lead for the NERC Environmental Data Service (EDS). The CEDA Archive is a vital part of the EDS, and we anticipate greater integration with other data centres as our collaboration deepens. Initiatives like the Data Stewardship Wizard exemplify our efforts to coordinate and streamline processes across the EDS.

Learning from our users and past events has been crucial. The work of the ESA Data Hub Relay has successfully progressed existing services and technologies, built on the foundations laid by previous successful endeavours. The JASMIN Group Workspace Scanner (GWS) now empowers users to manage and tidy their own data, and lessons from an extended JASMIN shutdown in October have informed ongoing measures to increase system robustness and availability. This also led to a review of our web services for better site resilience, and the introduction of a dedicated [status page site](#) to streamline user communication.

This year
we responded
to over
3,500
user queries

People working inside the FAAM aircraft. CEDA has a long relationship with the FAAM team archiving data from flights and making it available to the user community. © National Centre for Atmospheric Science

Data Stewardship Wizard: streamlining data management

WENDY GARLAND

In accordance with NERC data policy, all NERC-funded projects should be considered for data management by a NERC Environmental Data Service (EDS) data centre. It is important that we approach data management consistently across the different centres. One way we collaborate is by sharing effort and knowledge and developing common tools. This year we have introduced the Data Stewardship Wizard (DSW) - a tool to collect and collate data management information and standardise the content and layout of the resulting data management plans.

The Data Stewardship Wizard guides users through the creation of a high-quality data management plan through a series of questions supported by an extensive knowledge base. It contains features that are useful to researchers as well as data stewards, such as tracking co-author contributions, easy updating, links to relevant guidelines, information resources, and the ability to export a Data Management Plan (DMP) in several formats.

A team from across the NERC EDS worked together to develop a set of questions aimed not only at gathering the relevant information but also encouraging project investigators to consider how their data should be formatted. This included a set of core questions about data requirements common to all data centres such as questions about licensing, access, and data products. There are also specialised questions depending on the data centre pertaining to discipline-specific concerns like data formats and quality assurance.

We are moving away from previous methods where data management plans were drafted by data centre staff through prolonged email exchanges with project leads, which could be tedious and time-consuming for all involved. Now, the onus has changed to empower project leads to create, populate, and produce their own DMP.

The Data Stewardship Wizard makes the project leads consider their data outputs including file formats, metadata, archiving locations and licensing information. This puts data in a central position for all projects and re-emphasises the need for good data quality.

The EDS deployed the DSW in December 2023. Since then, the Data Stewardship Wizard has been used to create data management plans for the majority of new NERC grants. It is hoped getting more engagement from the project leads at the early stages will reap more engagement in the archiving stage.

The tool was originally developed by ELIXIR - a European life sciences infrastructure. The UK Centre for Ecology and Hydrology which hosts the Environmental Information Data Centre (EIDC) led the implementation and customisation of this tool for the EDS. CEDA played a pivotal role in discussions during the implementation and ensured that questions asked were relevant and worded concisely.

Discipline: Marine

Discipline: Atmospheric, Earth, Observation and Solar and Space physics

Discipline: Terrestrial and Freshwater

Discipline: Geoscience

Discipline: Polar and Cryosphere

Image shows the 5 data centres that make up the NERC Environmental Data Service: British Oceanographic Data Centre, Centre for Environmental Data Analysis, Environmental Information Data Centre, National Geoscience Data Centre, and the UK Polar Data Centre.

**“ JASMIN, it’s
like the air,
if it went away
it would be a
real problem.”**

JASMIN user from the University of Reading

Machine room in Scientific Computing
Department, STFC showing the JASMIN
supercomputer © National Centre for
Atmospheric Science

JASMIN Update: expanding infrastructure and overcoming challenges

ADRIAN HINES, MATT PRITCHARD

JASMIN remains at the core of the technology and innovation work undertaken within CEDA, providing the computational infrastructure needed to support both the work within the team and the data storage and processing capacity to support a community that spans the full breadth of environmental science research and beyond. This community has continued to grow, in part due to the strategic aim of UKRI to move towards a more coherent cross-council digital research infrastructure.

For the JASMIN team, the year has been characterised by a mixture of ups and downs, often happening in parallel. An extended outage, for nearly two weeks in November as a result of essential power supply maintenance work, highlighted the reliance of some of the community on the high availability of JASMIN. Whilst this caused some disruption to users, it has enabled us to reset expectations about the nature of JASMIN as a research infrastructure, and has initiated a useful dialogue about resilience requirements and how to balance those requirements with the cost of operating the service.

The extended outage coincided with the first in-person JASMIN users conference since the Covid pandemic. With around 40 external users joining the JASMIN and CEDA teams over 2 days, this provided an opportunity for some excellent in-depth conversations, which enabled us to update our users, and to gather their feedback.

The general external environment in relation to the support and maintenance of JASMIN hardware has been challenging, with sharp increases in some costs, and changes in the external marketplace. This was most evident through difficulties in procuring ongoing support for the underlying platform used in the JASMIN Cloud services, with the consequence of an unexpectedly urgent move to a new solution, based on the use of STFC Cloud.

On a positive note, a proposal to the UKRI Digital Research Infrastructure Phase 2 call was successful, securing £9m of additional investment between December 2023 and March 2025. These funds, together with other capital budgets, enabled an investment of £5.7m in replacement CPU cores for the LOTUS cluster, allowing the expansion of the cluster from c. 18,000 cores to c. 55,000 cores. This will provide a big boost in the compute power available to the user community.

Attendees at the JASMIN User Conference 2023 sat around tables during one of the discussion sessions, talking about things we can do to reduce JASMIN's environmental impact © National Centre for Atmospheric Science

We manage over
400
active group workspaces
on JASMIN with over
24 Petabytes
of storage allocated
to them

Group Workspace Scanner: a tool to efficiently manage collaborative data

NICOLA FARMER

Effective data management is vital for collaborative projects, especially when dealing with vast amounts of data. A Group Workspace (GWS) is a collaborative storage area, on JASMIN, made available to a group for a project. Each GWS has a manager responsible for administering the storage of this collaborative area. This task can present a significant challenge and so the Group Workspace Scanner, an interactive web application, has been developed to address this need. It helps JASMIN users easily navigate and manage their group workspaces, ensuring optimal use of allocated storage.

The Group Workspace Scanner has been part of a push to help users understand what data they have stored, and recover space from data stored which isn't needed any more. This is important as recovering storage space allows better use of our resources and, by reducing the amount of space we need to make available, our impact on the environment.

How it works

The Group Workspace Scanner is made up of two parts: a scanner that collects data, and a user interface that presents it. The scanner runs automatically in the background, scanning each group workspace approximately every two weeks to gather essential usage information. This data is stored in a database and displayed through the user interface.

The user interface presents the data from the scanner clearly in the form of a tree graph. The tree graph which shows the structure of the group workspace, allowing users to explore folders and subfolders. You can adjust the graph to highlight different aspects such as size, file count, or activity ('heat'). Additionally, doughnut graphs provide additional detailed breakdowns by user, file type and activity, offering insights into how space is used and by which users.

Benefits for users

The Group Workspace Scanner is particularly beneficial for group workspace managers who need to optimise storage use, but it's also useful for any JASMIN user looking to understand their data usage patterns. By providing detailed insights into file distribution and usage, the scanner helps identify opportunities to free up space and manage resources more effectively.

Work on the scanner is part of an ongoing activity to help monitor current group workspace usage, update records of active projects and reclaim unused space. It is important to provide tools and information to empower group workspace managers and users to make conscious decisions about how and where they store data.

The Group Workspace Scanner is now available for all JASMIN users. Visit gws-scanner.jasmin.ac.uk to start exploring your group workspaces. For detailed guidance, check out [the comprehensive documentation](#) on our JASMIN help docs website.

GWS Scanner tree diagram showing the contents of the GWS as coloured tiles labelled with their name, size and number of children.

GWS Scanner donut diagram showing a user, filetype and heat breakdown for the GWS.

Improving resilience and efficiency of our websites

JESSE ALEXANDER, MATT PRITCHARD

Whilst the JASMIN shutdown in October 2023 presented some unique challenges to us and our users, having a period of advanced notice gave us an opportunity to examine some of our outward-facing web services and to consider how and where they are hosted.

Many web-based services operated by CEDA and JASMIN are hosted on JASMIN itself as they need to interact with local resources such as project databases or the CEDA Archive. The power outage, and the break in connectivity to JASMIN-hosted resources that it caused, meant that we had to review where we hosted essential public-facing sites, particularly the [CEDA website](#) as it is used to share news items and other updates with our community.

This review led us to the decision to move the [JASMIN website](#) to a cloud-hosted platform. In doing so it gave us the opportunity to rethink the site and change its structure from a Python/Django-based web application to a static site. This gave many benefits including an easier process for making content, since it can be written in simple Markdown and built into HTML by a static site generator (in this case, [Jekyll](#), coupled with [Github Pages](#)).

This was advantageous as there is no “server” to manage, just templates and a cloud-hosted build process which is run whenever updates are applied. This means the resulting site is faster to load, more resilient, and stays up when JASMIN is out of service.

Considering the same type of migration for the CEDA site, we had some key concerns:

- We needed to move quickly to ensure we had a way of communicating with users during the power outage.
- There was a lot more content to migrate, ie. news & events going back multiple decades.
- We needed a template system ideally based on the familiar Bootstrap frontend framework used for all our other web applications.
- The best static site template would have good accessibility, usability, and provide useful information with a fresh look and feel.

The chosen solution was the [Hugo](#) static site generator, coupled with the [Hinode](#) theme package. This fitted the bill for both the CEDA website and [JASMIN help documentation site](#) which we later migrated to the same system, and the JASMIN site itself will probably be migrated in due course, to consolidate.

Rebuilding the site also allowed us to rethink how we deliver status updates to our users. We wanted to introduce a status page for CEDA & JASMIN, to provide service updates in a concise form, maintained in one place and separate from news items.

From here we made the [CEDA status page](#), a single place to see all the current status reports and any future incidents that might affect our systems or services. When this page loads it fetches the latest status information from a JSON file in a separate repository. This allows us to quickly add service announcements without having to wait for the site to re-build. Overall the work in moving these services to cloud-hosted, static sites, and the templating system adopted, has meant that the sites are more secure, attractive, resilient and easier to maintain. This means that we can spend less time managing them and more time using them to communicate with our users.

The homepage of the new and improved CEDA website. With a sleek header and nicely displayed news items. Screenshot of our new Status page, showing incidents currently affecting our services and future scheduled maintenance that could impact users

Sentinel Data Hub Relay gets renewed for Phase 2!

STEVE DONEGAN, ED WILLIAMSON

CEDA has run a Sentinel Data Hub Relay (DHR) under contract to the European Space Agency (ESA) since April 2021. The purpose of this is to facilitate the large transfer of Copernicus Earth observation data from Sentinel satellites to National Mirror Archive Sites. This is done via the ESA Relay Hub Network. Our role is to supply extra capacity and resiliency in this network and provide a convenient source for retrieving data to the Sentinel Mirror archive at CEDA. Currently, we have retrieved more than 20PB of data, of which 8PB has been retrieved for the mirror archive for the benefit of CEDA users. Furthermore, we have relayed almost 2PB to other DHRs in the wider network.

We have worked closely with the ESA to ensure the efficient and timely operation of the DHR. Throughout Phase 1 of the DHR project, which ran from April 2021 to June 2024, we consistently met the product latency and DHR availability Key Performance Indicators. Thanks to our strong performance as part of ESA's DHR network our contract was renewed. This allowed us to move forward into Phase 2 of the project in February 2024 extending the collaboration for an additional two years.

This 1st phase of the relay hub project was primarily concerned with the retrieval and onward relaying of Sentinel data, guaranteeing data dissemination within the ESA network. As part of the phase 1 work, CEDA has worked with ESA and other partners to test components of the new ESA Data Hub Software (DHS) in preparation for phase 2 which includes the active rollout of the DHS. The DHS will incorporate newer methodologies for the retrieval and onward transfer of data consistent with the latest technologies.

The DHS at CEDA will be based around a set of containers within a dedicated Docker Swarm installation. This configuration allows the data retrieval component to be dynamically assigned greater resources when required, improving the stability and resilience of the service. This feature will become even more vital as new Sentinels come online in the next 2 years which will significantly increase the volume of incoming Sentinel data.

The new Data Hub Software provides individual components that improve the service for all users, whereas previously all functionality was handled by the monolithic DHuS interface. This allows for a more dynamic and stable service operation. For example, The Copernicus Space Component Interface (COPSI) provides a front-end graphical user interface allowing users improved functionality and the latest protocols for API access. The Dataflow Network Environment (DAFNE) component will allow enhanced monitoring and data flow reporting providing more consistent reporting across the Data Hub Relays. The new DHS will come online in Autumn 2024.

New COPSI GUI interface for querying data in DHS at CEDA

Collaboration, expertise and skills-sharing

WENDY GARLAND

This year, we've spent time examining the way we work and how we can improve our internal processes and working patterns. We undertook Agile training which reframed the way we tackle projects and has had a big impact on the quality of products we deliver to our users.

We have also moved to a new office on site, one which is bigger, open-plan and has hot-desking. This new workspace provides much more opportunity for face-to-face interactions, brainstorming and collaborations. We are also more able to ask each for help and advice due to the hot-desking mixing up who we interact with in the team.

CEDA has always been a collaborative organisation. Working closely with external partners and leveraging our expertise, we are drivers of innovation and support key projects like the Earth Observation Datahub. Collaboration allows us to learn from others, bringing new perspectives and knowledge that positively impact both our staff and the services we provide for the environmental science community.

As well as sharing technical expertise, the breadth of domain knowledge held by our staff also provides opportunities for collaboration, such as the workshop run this year with Climateurope2 about communicating uncertainty in the context of climate change.

We encourage our team members to expand their skill sets, and this year many of our staff members have had this opportunity, either by pursuing academic qualifications or participating in external placements. These experiences not only enrich their individual capabilities but also bring fresh insights back to their roles, benefiting the wider team.

Together we work to ensure that we remain agile, forward-thinking, and capable of meeting the evolving needs of our communities. By learning from others and applying those learnings, we continue to strengthen both our organisation and the impact we have on the environmental science community.

Members of the CEDA team standing proudly behind the Lego city they constructed using an Agile methodology

The challenges of communicating uncertainty in the context of climate change

CHARLOTTE PASCOE

[Climateurope2](#) has an ambition to standardise climate services and that includes uncertainty. However, uncertainty can mean different things depending on the context.

CEDA staff organised a workshop with Climateurope2 on [communicating climate uncertainty](#) to find out how uncertainty was being communicated in different sectors of the climate information value chain: from national weather services, to risk assessment enterprises down to local decision-makers who need to make their infrastructure and land use planning more resilient to our changing climate.

Perhaps the most unusual lesson we learned was not to talk about uncertainty at all. There are many ways in which uncertainty can be inferred. For instance, by showing the consequences of just two different climate scenarios, it is understood that there is uncertainty about what the future climate has in store.

Breaking down uncertainty

From a data provision perspective, uncertainty quantification and communication can be considered in terms of different aspects. The aspect of the uncertainty will determine the type of communication. For instance, a statistical level of uncertainty that is typical of weather forecasts can be communicated with graphs, whereas a scenario level of uncertainty would be better communicated with a narrative or storyline approach.

Scenarios are used to understand climate change on generational timescales. The climate our children will experience in their lifetimes depends on policy choices that are being made now. At those timescales, uncertainty about how we, as humans, play our part in the climate system is one of the biggest unknowns.

Tailor uncertainty communication to the user

Placing the user at the centre of the communication means that we can tailor the information to their concerns. For instance, if resilience to extreme events is the most important aspect of climate change to the user, the scenario uncertainty can be reduced by constraining the analysis to only those scenarios that manifest the extreme events of concern. However, any assumptions or analysis methods that constrain the uncertainty context must be communicated transparently alongside the findings.

We need standards for uncertainty communication

Communicating uncertainty that is relevant to the user in a clear way can be an important tool for building trust. When climate risks remain obvious despite the uncertainties, more confidence can be placed in the assessment and bolder choices can be made.

Given the many different aspects of uncertainty, a key challenge of uncertainty communication is to be transparent without confusing users, especially when different datasets are being combined. If a user has different uncertainty information from different channels it can become confusing and trust may be lost. This is an area where standards and protocols have the potential to bring much-needed clarity.

So what's next?

We'll be focusing on outreach in the coming months to find out how different sectors are using climate information, what their unique needs are and where those needs overlap. With this, we aim to develop strategies for the delivery of information about climate uncertainty.

The Earth Observation DataHub – revolutionising access to data for government, academia, and industry

FEDERICA MOSCATO

The [Earth Observation DataHub \(EODH\)](#) is a pioneering initiative in the UK, designed to facilitate access to Earth Observation data for government, business and academia. This project aims to enhance decision-making processes across various sectors by integrating high-quality, space-derived data that provides valuable insights.

CEDA staff are leading the project management, overseeing its technical direction and the day-to-day logistics of working with many partners. In particular, the CEDA team is leading the procurement of the EO Data Hub platform. This will serve as a core system, managing data and services, with a portion of CEDA's archive being integrated into it. Additionally, three separate applications will be built on top of this platform, each designed to facilitate different types of access, analysis, and interaction with the Hub, for which CEDA is leading the procurement.

EODH is a two-year project, ending in 2025, aiming to provide a single point of access to the best UK Earth observation data, which can be utilised by researchers, government bodies, and businesses. The platform is being developed with input from business, academia, and government sectors to ensure it meets a wide range of needs. It features dedicated applications and products that will be available for end-user testing in Autumn 2024.

Overall, the EODH is set to transform access to Earth Observation data, making it more efficient, sustainable, and authoritative, supporting a wide array of stakeholders in making informed, data-driven decisions. It will implement a unique UK service that will federate data access and provide centralised software services to bring value across the breadth of sector users.

Target Users and Benefits

Government and Public Sector

The EODH serves as a centralised platform that allows different government departments to share Earth Observation data cost-effectively. This shared access helps ensure consistency in policy creation, adoption, and monitoring, which in turn supports citizen protection. By providing collective purchasing power, the platform helps reduce costs and enhances the efficiency of governmental operations.

Academia

For the academic community, the EODH offers collaboration opportunities and access to extensive time-series data, which is critical for scientific research. The hub provides advanced workflows that allow researchers to focus more on scientific exploration and analysis, contributing to the generation of trustworthy data.

Industry

Businesses benefit from the EODH by gaining insights into environmental risks, both local and global. Access to authoritative data is crucial for businesses in making informed decisions regarding investment planning, due diligence, and regulatory compliance. The platform will support businesses in understanding the implications of environmental changes on their operations.

Funding and partners

The EODH is funded approximately £10 million by NERC through the Earth Observation Investment Package provided by the Department for Science, Innovation and Technology.

The consortium is led by the National Centre for Earth Observation including staff from CEDA and the University of Leicester, and public-funded partners in the Satellite Applications Catapult, the UK Met Office, the National Physical Laboratory. It also has industrial partners delivering the project software and data infrastructure.

CEDA’s leadership in Continuous Improvement

WILLIAM TUCKER

This year, CEDA has been engaged in a department-wide project focusing on incremental improvements to our software development practices. Continuous Improvement is a term that encompasses a variety of techniques and philosophies that aim to make incremental improvements to the internal workings of an organisation, by reducing waste and improving efficiency.

After this project was suggested by a staff member, an investigation within RAL Space, our host department, found inefficiencies in our software processes which were negatively affecting our performance. CEDA was approached to lead this project due to our expertise and large team of developers. One of our senior developers, William Tucker, volunteered to lead this project.

To begin making improvements we needed to understand the development landscape across RAL Space. The first step involved sending out a survey to all staff to gather feedback on the type of software development activities they are involved with. From this, we could identify key developers and project managers involved in software projects across the department.

A 1-day workshop was held in June, where we invited these individuals to share their views on the most important issues and discuss what approaches could be taken to address them. We brainstormed ideas for how we could improve the effectiveness of our software delivery.

These issues were then distilled into problem statements, with the principle one being a lack of collaboration between groups; each department tackles software development differently, which leads to difficulty communicating ideas and best practice between groups. There was also a lack of understanding about pre-existing tools and resources which are available to staff, creating duplication of work.

At CEDA, we’ve taken steps to tackle these issues and ensure that our processes reflect the goals we’re striving for. We are looking to train more of our staff in continuous improvement so we all have the skills to undertake our own CEDA-focused improvement projects.

The next thing we’d like to address is user feedback we’ve received regarding the usability and accessibility of our services. From our experience with continuous improvement, we now know it’s important to do a formal evaluation of the issues users are facing in order to identify their root causes and possible solutions.

STFC Continuous Improvement Celebration

In October, RAL Space had a strong presence at a Continuous Improvement celebration event held by STFC. The event highlighted the success of numerous improvement projects from throughout the department, including the project we led. These ranged from workspace improvements for engineers to efficiency gains in procurement leading to £25M+ in savings. We’re pleased that STFC is taking continuous improvement seriously, and are excited to get involved in these activities more in the future.

STFC Staff members holding certificates for their great CI work at the Continuous Improvement celebration event in October 2023

Staff learning and development

HAYLEY GRAY, AG STEPHENS, EMILY ANDERSON, MOLLY MACRAE, NICOLA FARMER

Supporting staff learning and development is key to enhancing our skillset at CEDA, encouraging the professional growth of our staff and ensuring that we remain adaptable and innovative in a rapidly changing environment. Here we highlight some learning opportunities that have been undertaken this year.

Supporting wider learning

BSc (Hons) Earth Science with the Open University

Hayley Gray, User Support and Metadata Services Operator

“ I have been studying towards an Earth Science degree which I completed this year, alongside working full time. The courses within this degree helped develop my skills in data collection, analysis, critical thinking and problem-solving. For my final project, I used Sentinel 1 data to detect the ground deformation around Mount Etna, an active volcano on the east coast of Sicily. Learning how to use Earth Observation datasets to support literature provided a great opportunity to support my career goals to be a Data Scientist within CEDA and gave me valuable experience working with datasets in our Archive. Since then, I have been writing a help document on how to use Sentinel data and associated software packages. I have also been using the skills gained from my studies to take on more data and archival tasks in my role at CEDA.

MSc in Artificial Intelligence at the University of Leeds

Ag Stephens, Head of Partnerships

“ I have been very fortunate to be able to return to part-time study to pursue a two-year Masters course in AI. The course covers the fundamentals from Data Science and Algorithms through to Machine and Deep Learning. I am also augmenting these studies with more domain-specific short courses that are relevant to our work within CEDA. We have set up a 'CEDA AI' group to discuss and investigate ways in which we might utilise AI to improve and extend our capabilities. Initially, we have focused on staff training to build an understanding of the foundations of supervised Machine Learning. Our next goals are to explore the use of AI approaches in our day-to-day work as well as supporting users of the ORCHID GPU-cluster on JASMIN which is designed for AI workflows. Early experimental mini-projects are looking at the use of Large Language Models (LLMs) as expert agents to answer user questions, and the possibility of training LLMs to understand and advise on common file formats such as CF-netCDF. On completion of my Masters, I hope to develop my role further so that I can assist our team and wider department in adopting relevant AI technologies and approaches where they will add demonstrable value.

CEDA placement students stood by the entrance to RAL Space

Graduate Placements

As part of the STFC graduate scheme, our graduates get the opportunity to complete a 3-month placement in another department, either within STFC or one of our partner organisations. This is a great way to gain skills and experience in a different role and workplace, and to build connections with our peers.

This year from January to March, three of our graduates from the 2022 cohort completed the following placements in climate research, software development, and project management.

The impacts of regional aerosol emissions on European climate – National Centre for Atmospheric Science, University of Reading

Molly MacRae, Graduate Environmental Data Scientist

“ I completed a research placement with scientists at the University of Reading exploring the impacts of future aerosol legislation on European climate. It was a great opportunity to experience a different academic environment, build connections with NCAS Reading and be a part of the research that CEDA supports. Returning to CEDA, I have continued this analysis and I am supporting the team in transferring their data to the CEDA Archive. I also had the opportunity to visit Oslo for a workshop with the research group!”

Enhancing CCP-EM Doppio User Interface for processing cryoEM data – Scientific Computing Department, STFC

Nicola Farmer, Graduate Software Developer

“ I completed a placement with the Collaborative Computational Project in Electron Microscopy (CCP-EM) group within the Scientific Computing Department at STFC. I spent my time working on a GUI called Doppio which is used by scientists for processing cryoEM data to look at protein structure. I enhanced the UI by adding the option to edit configuration settings from within a dialogue box in the UI using TypeScript and wrote tests for the content I added using Jest. It was a great opportunity to gain some experience with these different programming languages. I came back to CEDA with broadened programming skills and with the knowledge of the testing framework Jest which I've since implemented in the JASMIN Projects Portal.”

Learning about Project Management with the RAL Space Imaging Systems Division, Project Management Group

Emily Anderson, Graduate Environmental Data Scientist

“ For my placement, I spent time with the Imaging Systems Project Management Group in RAL Space where I managed a project called 'HARMONI' which is a spectrograph being built for the Extremely Large Telescope. Throughout my placement, I encountered many different tasks and skills used within project management. This included stakeholder engagement, internal communications, resource management and budgeting. I even got to go inside the cleanrooms! It was great to learn more about what other RAL Space teams get up to, as well as working with completely different people for a few months. Back at CEDA, I am utilising the skills that I learnt whilst on placement by helping with a wide range of project management tasks.”

“JASMIN is enabling loads and loads of science that would not otherwise get done.”

Climate model developer at the University of Cambridge

Fatima Chami inspects JASMIN computer servers at Rutherford Appleton Laboratory © National Centre for Atmospheric Science

Implementing new research

GRAHAM PARTON

Throughout CEDA's history, the ever-evolving data curation and exploitation needs of the community we serve have always required CEDA to push forward development on standards, technologies, techniques and services.

This section of the annual report provides insights into a range of new research undertaken over the last year. Some build upon external research such as trialling frameworks or the use of new data formats, whilst others have seen CEDA uncover and lead significant improvements driven by our communities' requirements which are now leading to wider community updates (e.g. our work with Elasticsearch and STAC).

Two key aspects, though, run as a common thread throughout all of CEDA's work: the engagement and knowledge exchange with the wider national and international research communities; and that CEDA's staff provide highly valued research contributions.

Whilst not all research may lead to operational services deployed by CEDA or the community, nonetheless, CEDA continues to gain insights and grow its experience to ensure that our staff enhance their valued reputation in the global research data, compute and environmental science communities.

Data from Chilbolton Observatory
is available on the CEDA Archive
© National Centre for Atmospheric Science

Cloud Optimised Formats for data access

DANIEL WESTWOOD

The archive of data we maintain at CEDA is growing at an ever-increasing rate, with the datasets themselves becoming larger and more detailed. To avoid lengthy and memory-intensive downloads or the requirement to be connected directly to JASMIN when accessing data, we are working to develop alternative ways to retrieve data. We hope this will make accessing data much easier and more efficient for our users. We have begun experimenting with new technologies, including so-called Cloud Optimised Formats – file formats adapted to make efficient use of object storage, which is a widely used form of storage available with cloud computing providers.

Kerchunk and Zarr are two of the most prevalent formats for cloud-accessible data. Kerchunk files are small reference files that map to specific parts of archived datasets and can be used to fetch only the parts of the data that are needed. By contrast, Zarr stores chunks of data in individual binary files and can serve only the specific files that are needed for a particular analysis. Both of these formats are supported in the popular Xarray package for data analysis.

CFA (Climate Forecast Aggregation) implemented in cf-python is an alternate aggregation method to both Kerchunk and Zarr where NetCDF data located in remote Object Storage can be accessed using a reference CFA-netCDF file. The CFA conventions for aggregation variables will be added to the CF conventions in a future update, and there are joint plans between CEDA and the University of Reading-based NCAS Computational Modelling Services (NCAS-CMS) group to develop an Xarray backend to enable the use of CFA-netCDF files within Xarray.

Given the rising popularity of these cloud formats, we have been developing a Python package called PADOCC to build these types of files for different datasets within the CEDA Archive. PADOCC (Pipeline to Aggregate Data for Optimised Cloud Capabilities) is capable of creating Kerchunk, Zarr and other cloud-optimised representations in parallel, utilising the JASMIN batch compute services, and in some cases can advise on the best format to use for different datasets. To date, PADOCC has been used to create 70 GB worth of Kerchunk files for over 6000 datasets, representing approximately 40 TB of archived NetCDF data.

Moving forward, it is hoped that PADOCC will become an integral part of the ingestion process for new data, such that we will produce cloud-accessible representations of a significant proportion of the data we collect. This will help make our data more FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable) and reduce excess resources needed to access datasets, lowering our carbon footprint.

JASMIN hardware that is maintained by our colleagues in STFC Scientific Computing © National Centre for Atmospheric Science

Making data discovery STAC up

RHYS EVANS

CEDA hosts over 25 Petabytes of atmospheric and Earth observation data. Sources include aircraft campaigns, satellites, automatic weather stations and climate models, amongst many others. The majority of the [CEDA Archive](#) is covered by 6 principal, well-documented and supported formats, like [NetCDF](#). Around 10% of file formats in the Archive are obfuscated due to file naming conventions in place at the time of ingestion. Some of these bespoke historic formats are no longer being supported by standard tooling, which makes the extraction of metadata for file discovery more difficult.

Several years ago we began searching for a flexible, scalable standard which would allow us to expose the bulk of the CEDA Archive via faceted search. The overall goal was to enhance our search services and user interfaces, as well as enabling greater collaboration with our national and international partners and communities. The [STAC](#) (Spatio Temporal Asset Catalogue) standard was initially developed for the Earth Observation community. As members of this community, alongside atmospheric science and Earth system modelling communities, we were interested to see whether STAC could fit our needs.

When CEDA first began investigating STAC's viability, the only database option for the community Application Programming Interface (API) was PostgreSQL. PostgreSQL is a traditional database and is not primarily designed for large-scale text-based search. In previous years, we had found success with Elasticsearch - a NoSQL solution which is scalable to meet our needs.

We developed an Elasticsearch-backed version of the STAC API, which has since become one of the core systems for the community API. CEDA has also been involved in developing several extensions to meet requirements that weren't already met by STAC's core and community functionality. We've found the open-source nature of this search standard as well as its active developer community has made for a more collaborative project.

CEDA's Archive needed to be scanned to generate the metadata required for the STAC records, similar to how search engines crawl the Web to index websites. While there were several existing packages these were project-specific and would not work across our Archive due to its heterogeneity. Therefore, we've developed a software package called the "[STAC generator](#)", which can be configured to run over any part of the CEDA Archive and extract project-specific information into a database running [ElasticSearch](#).

We now feel confident that STAC is a viable solution to our search requirements. As such, we have begun to curate a STAC catalogue with a subset of CEDA's data. In the future, we plan to ingest more data and unify our search services to this standard to improve discovery and provide access to more standardised tools for our users. It is hoped that the move to a recognised external standard will yield better interoperability with existing and new projects.

Jon Robson with illuminated globe
© National Centre for Atmospheric Science

The EOEPKA Framework: should we integrate it with our services?

MATT JONES

The [Earth Observation Exploitation Platform Common Architecture \(EOEPKA\)](#) is a project, sponsored by the European Space Agency, to develop a common framework for Earth Observation (EO) data exploitation platforms, following Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC) standards and best practice. The project aimed to develop a common framework for Earth Observation (EO) data exploitation platforms, following [Open Geospatial Consortium \(OGC\)](#) standards and best practice. Its objectives were to create a standardised and interoperable infrastructure, which is accessible and easy to use by a wide range of users. This includes non-research users through the European Space Agency (ESA) [Network of Resources](#) which connects users to cloud-based platforms, data processing tools, and storage resources. CEDA staff trialled the use of this framework, here we summarise our findings.

- User and access management using OpenID Connect
- Data visualisation
- A data catalogue using OpenSearch
- Data processing with the Application Execution and Deployment Service (ADES)
- Data staging using object storage

EOEPKA is designed to facilitate easier access and exploitation of EO data and is composed of numerous core services, including:

A platform like this which focuses on interoperability and open data standards aligns closely with CEDA's aim for more accessible user-centric services. With this in mind, we set out with three goals:

- 1. Assess the use of EOEPKA and the ESA Network of Resources on a research platform (JASMIN)**
- 2. Integrate the ADES for data processing with our batch processing cluster using the SLURM scheduler**
- 3. Integrate a sub-setting tool for ESA Climate Change Initiative (CCI) data held in the CEDA Archive.**

We successfully deployed a development version of the EOEPKA platform in the JASMIN external cloud and integrated it with a SLURM cluster created by our [Cluster-as-a-Service](#) system. We provided this as an open-source contribution back to the project. We also adapted a subsetting tool that was developed previously under a C3S Climate Data Store contract for use with a docker container and common workflow language to give users a convenient way to subset CCI data in the Archive.

This project gave us the opportunity to investigate how we could make SLURM available externally to non-JASMIN users and to assess whether EOEPKA could be a valuable addition to what we already offer through the CEDA Archive and JASMIN.

Whilst it could give a route to expose data and processing services to users who are not eligible to use JASMIN, the use by existing JASMIN and CEDA users would be limited considering the extra overhead of getting their workflows running on the EOEPKA platform. These users already have routes to explore and access the data held in the CEDA Archive. Therefore, we decided not to progress to a production deployment. However, we learnt a lot from this project, and look forward to interactions with similar projects in the future.

An aerial photograph showing a coastline with a large body of water on the right and a forested area on the left. The sky is blue with some clouds. The image is used as a background for the text.

“CMIP is the best thing there is for understanding climate change on a global scale and capturing the full range of model uncertainty.”

CMIP Data User

Experimenting with user engagement methods

POPPY TOWNSEND, CHARLOTTE PASCOE, MOLLY MACRAE, WENDY GARLAND

The Environmental Data Service (EDS) is working to coordinate the data, tools and services provided by the individual NERC data centres so that users can access them via a single interface. This work is creating the infrastructure needed to make data interoperability a reality for all EDS data holdings, both NERC-managed and externally provided.

The EDS Enhancement project made progress towards this goal by building on existing knowledge. CEDA led the 'Communications, Use Cases and Project Management' work package, analysing end-to-end workflow of data from collection to user application, for which three use cases were identified:

- Extensive work, including surveys and focus groups, was undertaken to better understand accessibility barriers to using data collected by the NERC **research aircraft**
- 1-1 interviews, with a 'snowballing technique' were used to investigate how the **climate modelling** community make use of CMIP data
- Interviews, workshops and a survey were used to better understand data management requirements for the **autonomous and remotely piloted aerial vehicles** community (led by the UK Polar Data Centre).

The three use cases explored how the ideas and developments delivered in the wider project can be applied to real data and trialled user engagement strategies that will help the EDS broaden its user base and enhance accessibility.

Two of the use cases were undertaken by CEDA (described below), while the third was undertaken by the UK Polar Data Centre ([you can find their report here](#)).

Understanding how the climate modelling community make use of data

The Coupled Model Intercomparison Project (CMIP) is a collaborative project of the World Climate Research Programme (WCRP) providing climate projections to understand past, present and future climate changes. The project is between its 6th and 7th phase. CEDA hosts a large subset of CMIP data as one of seven nodes that store and distribute the data globally. The team spoke with 11 CMIP data users at various research institutions and career stages to gain an understanding of what the community feels could be improved about the data service and obstacles to data access.

The discussions focused on past experiences with the data and expectations for future data access to CMIP7. The 'snowballing technique' was an effective way to build up a network of people to talk to starting from a few known initial contacts, and broadening to include early career researchers with a newer perspective to CMIP data access.

Exploring accessibility barriers to using aircraft data

Data from the UK based FAAM research aircraft is archived at CEDA with an open-access licence. This makes engaging with users in order to ask for feedback problematic as we do not know who they are.

This work aimed to gain enhanced understanding of the user base, their accessibility barriers and how to overcome them. This work experimented with two different strategies for engaging with unknown users: surveys and focus groups.

Overall we gathered useful information about the barriers to accessing aircraft data. However it came from a small sample of users, so may not be representative. With limited staff resources we found it difficult to reach out to unknown users as it was very time-consuming. The information we managed to gather has sparked new ideas for improvements to data access and will hopefully help remove some barriers for this particular dataset. Future work could look to implement some of the solutions proposed.

This year our users downloaded

70
million files

totalling more than a petabyte of data.

That's the equivalent of streaming HD films non-stop for over 15 years!

Metrics, Finance, Projects and Outputs

CHARLOTTE PASCOE

CEDA's key goal is to ensure that we are providing the best possible service to our user communities and enabling cutting-edge environmental science research. The previous sections in this report have spotlighted some of the amazing work we've done, projects we've supported, and challenges we have overcome. This final section details our key usage metrics followed by finance and project details. It also lists our other outputs: publications, posters and talks followed by a list of training delivered by CEDA staff during 2023-24.

There are
currently over
2,000
active
JASMIN users

Sarah Summers runs maintenance on JASMIN computer servers at Rutherford Appleton Laboratory © National Centre for Atmospheric Science

Summary and usage information

CEDA exists to support the atmospheric, Earth observation and near-Earth environment research communities in the UK and abroad through the provision of data management and access services. CEDA enhances this role through the development and maintenance of tools and services to aid data preservation, curation, discovery and visualisation; all of which add value for the worldwide user community.

The JASMIN data analysis facility provides petascale data-compute capabilities for the UK and wider environmental research communities. This section of the annual report presents summaries of CEDA Archive and JASMIN usage.

Data Archive Service

CEDA delivers Data Archive services for the National Centre for Atmospheric Science (NCAS), the National Centre for Earth Observation (NCEO) and the NERC/STFC-funded UK Solar System Data Centre (UKSSDC), as part of the NERC Environmental Data Service (EDS).

Data Curation

441 new datasets have been created and made available via the [CEDA catalogue](#) – bringing the total number of datasets to 9421 (as of Apr 2024). 195 new [DOIs were issued](#) in this period, bringing the number of DOled resources to 824 (as of Apr 2024).

Annual CEDA Archive Deposits: April 2023 to March 2024

Total volume deposited	2.6PB
Total number of files deposited	13,557,880

The Archive now holds over 23.1 Petabytes of data in 358,233,787 files.

Usage of CEDA Data

Annual CEDA Archive Usage: April 2023 to March 2024

Total number of users/distinct IP addresses	35,007
Total data downloaded	1.03PB
Total number of accesses	70,224,265
Number of datasets with downloads	6,663

Table: Summary figures for usage by CEDA consumers during the reporting year.

Note that a considerable amount of use of CEDA Archive data is by users on JASMIN, who would not be measured in most of these statistics because the data is directly available on the file system (and we are currently unable to gather these metrics).

For datasets requiring users to register for access, additional demographics (geographical area and institute type) are available. Note though, that many datasets are fully open so do not require user registration: those users are not captured here, unless they happen to have registered and logged in.

	New users period 2023-24	5-year period 2018-23
Registrations	8,465	39,782
% new users from the UK	52%	57%
% new users in Universities	63%	74%

Table: New registered users statistics for the reporting year and preceding 5-year period.

Usage of JASMIN

JASMIN delivers analysis and compute capability for the environmental science community, predominantly for NCAS and NCEO, but also supports other NERC domains: oceanography, polar science, geology and earth sciences, ecology and hydrology.

As of March 2024 there are:

- Over 2,080 active JASMIN users
- Over 400 shared group workspaces, with over 24 Petabytes of storage allocated to them.
- Over 50 tenancies in the JASMIN community cloud

General overview

Supporting our users

There were 3599 queries received by the helpdesk (covering both CEDA Archive and JASMIN services). These queries cover all aspects of data support except dataset/service applications or long-term data management discussions.

833 applications were processed for access to restricted datasets.

Collaborations

CEDA works closely with STFC's [Scientific Computing Department](#) to deliver the JASMIN infrastructure.

In 2023/2024, significant national and international collaborations have continued to support the international climate modelling community, Earth Observation and atmospheric research. On the national scale, CEDA itself reflects a collaboration between the earth observation community, the atmospheric sciences community (via [NCEO](#) and [NCAS](#)) and the space weather community.

Additionally, CEDA is:

1. Working closely with the other NERC Environmental Data Centres, as part of the [NERC Environmental Data Service](#).
2. Operating and evolving the Earth System Grid Federation ([ESGF](#)) in partnership with ENES and global network of climate data service providers led by [Oak Ridge National Laboratory](#) and the [US Programme for Climate Model Diagnosis and Intercomparison](#) in support of the sixth Coupled Model Intercomparison Project (CMIP).
3. Working with the wider UK atmospheric science and earth observation communities, via a range of projects, with [NCAS](#) and other [NERC](#) funding.
4. Working with the European Space Agency on projects such as the [ESA Climate Change Initiative \(CCI\)](#) Knowledge Exchange.
5. Delivering part of the UK Collaborative Ground Segment for Sentinel data (with [UK Space Agency](#), [Airbus](#), [Satellite Applications Catapult](#)) with the role to provide Sentinel data mirror archives and data processing capability for the UK academic community.
6. Operating a Data Hub Relay (DHR) on behalf of ESA as a fully functioning member of the ESA DHR network. This supports CEDA use of this for Copernicus data retrievals for the CEDA Mirror Archive.
7. Representing the UK internationally on the inter-space agency CEOS data group (WGISS) via a CEDA staff member and being actively involved in WGISS Jupyter Notebooks Best Practice workstream, organizing and leading [CEOS Jupyter Notebooks Day](#) – Supporting Global Best Practice and Training.
8. Supporting the preparation and running of the PV 2023 conference.
9. Working with [ECMWF](#) to provide EO scientists with the high-resolution atmospheric analyses they need to process satellite observations.
10. Disseminating climate and weather data to the research community, working with colleagues in the [UK Met Office](#).

- 11. Supporting the [Climate and Forecast Metadata \(CF\) Conventions](#) with partners in [University of Reading](#), [UK Met Office](#), and multiple US research institutions.
- 12. Working with academic partners in the [UK Research and Innovation](#) Cloud Working Group and NERC Digital Research Infrastructure Group to share best practice, knowledge and strategy for use of cloud computing in the research domain.
- 13. Working with the [CMIP Panel](#), the [WGCM Infrastructure Panel](#), and a range of CMIP Task Forces to develop the collaborative framework for the next phase of CMIP and with the [IPCC Task Group on Data \(TG-DATA\)](#) to ensure transparency and clear lines of provenance for data cited in the IPCC Assessment Reports.
- 14. Working with the [Research Data Alliance](#) to develop and advance FAIR data standards and research data management practices and career pathways.
- 15. Working with [Climateurope2](#) to build a community of practice for the standardisation and support of equitable, quality-assured climate services for society.

Funding

In addition to supporting NCAS and NCEO, CEDA also delivers major projects with funding from a range of other bodies, including work for the European Space Agency ([ESA](#)), [DSIT](#), [Defra](#) and others, as well as participating and coordinating major European projects.

Annual total funding

Financial Year	13-14	14-15	15-16	16-17	17-18	18-19	19-20	20-21	21-22	22-23	23-24
NCAS income	829	829	808	808	808	808	808	808	808	813	1184
NCEO income	392	390	393	393	393	402	393	418	393	396	408
Other NERC income	272	600	621	825	816	733	883	784	1371	1789	1663
Other income	1486	1394	1505	1092	1280	1458	1377	1476	1391	1590	1755
Total income	2979	3213	3327	3118	3297	3401	3461	3486	3963	4588	5010

Table: Overall funding for CEDA for financial years 2013/14 to 2023/24 (in £k)

Most of this funding comes to CEDA via contracts with NCAS and NCEO, with some via a service level agreement (SLA) between NERC and STFC.

Sustainable Airborne Research and Atmospheric Science Symposium © National Centre for Atmospheric Science

Externally funded projects

The table below shows CEDA's externally funded projects which were active during the reporting year.

Name	Description	Funder	Start date	End date	Value (£k)
EO DataHub	Collaborative project involving public sector and industry partners to develop a UK digital infrastructure for the exploitation of Earth Observation data to support industry, public sector and the research community	DSIT	01/02/2023	31/03/2025	9,931 (Actual budget for CEDA Staff: 1,016)
ESA CCI Knowledge Exchange	Data archive for ESA Climate Change Initiative as part of wider activity including outreach and education	ESA	5/9/2019	29/08/2024	763.8
ESA Data Hub Relay	Operation of a Sentinel Data Hub Relay for ESA	ESA	01/04/2021	31/08/2024	739.1
MOHC Data Pipeline	Continuation of the MOHC Data Pipeline that supports the transfer, cataloguing, publication and dissemination of the Met Office Hadley Centre climate simulations	Met Office	01/04/2021	31/03/2024	450.0
EO Data Architecture	Funding for the UKSA Call for strategy on EO Data Architecture	UKSA via Telespazio	01/03/2022	30/04/2022	19.9
UKRI Net Zero Digital Research Infrastructure	Scoping project to investigate how UKRI can achieve net zero computing	UKRI	01/11/2021	30/06/2023	487.4
Net Zero DRI 2023b	Additional funding to continue the work of the UKRI Net Zero DRI Scoping Project	UKRI	01/07/2023	31/03/2024	47
CCI Obs4MIPS CMUG Phase2	Involvement in reporting on future requirements for the evolution of Obs4MIPs	ESA	01/04/2022	31/08/2026	48.8
ClimatEurope2	Horizon Europe project on standards for climate services	EC	01/09/2022	28/02/27	88
EOEPCA Op Uptake Support	Deploying EOEPCA software onto JASMIN to make CEDA data available to EOEPCA	ESA	01/07/2022	30/06/2024	64.5
Horizon EERIE Data Services	Data Management and Publication for European Eddy-Rich Earth-System models	EC	01/03/2023	31/12/2026	112.8
JASMIN for CCI+ Lakes 22-25	Funding for the use of JASMIN resources	ESA via the University of Reading	01/04/2023	31/03/2025	16.6
NAME WPS Support	Providing support to enable the NAME model application to run on the WPS	Met Office	01/01/2023	31/03/2024	20

Table: Externally funded projects with a value greater than £15k for 2023/24 (non-core NERC)

CEDA publications list for AR 23/24

Anderson, E., MacRae, M., Pascoe, C., Sitz, L., Cammarano, D., Pirani, A., Stockhouse, M., Implementing FAIR principles in the IPCC context to support open science and provide a citable platform to acknowledge the work of authors (Poster), PV2023 Conference, CERN, May 2023.

Dębski, A., Parton, G. (2023). cedadev/cedadocs_migrate: v1.0.0 (Initial). Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7611795>

Evans, R., STAC for CEDA - Developing a scalable, standards-based search system (Presentation), PV2023 Conference, CERN, May 2023.

Fisher, E., Pascoe, C. Presentation to IPCC TG-Data to present what CEDA has done with IPCC figure data archiving & our progress, challenges etc. August 2022

Juckes, M., Bane, M., Bulpett, J., Cartmell, K., MacFarlane, M., MacRae, M., Owen, A., Pascoe, C., & Townsend, P. (2023). Sustainability in Digital Research Infrastructure: UKRI Net Zero DRI Scoping Project final technical report. Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8199984>

Kershaw, P. & Remedios, J. (2023). The EO DataHub. (Presentation)
<https://doi.org/10.13140/rg.2.2.25731.31527>

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<https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.35797.64483>

MacRae, M., MacFarlane, M., Townsend, P., Cartmell, K., Pascoe, C., & Juckes, M. (2023). Interactive recommendations and action list for technical report from the UKRI Net Zero DRI Scoping Project (Data set). Zenodo.
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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8203117>

Massey, N., Leland, J., Lawrence, B., A scalable near line storage solution for very big data (Presentation), EGU General Assembly, April 2023.

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Strommen, K., **MacRae, M.,** & Christensen, H. (2023). On the relationship between reliability diagrams and

the "signal-to-noise paradox". Geophysical Research Letters, 50, e2023GL103710.
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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10707219>

Pamment, A. (2024, February 21). CF Standard Names - Update for CF 2023 workshop. Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10687611>

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Training/Events

All events run or supported by CEDA are shown below – [for further information check out our website.](#)

RAL Space Software Continuous improvement workshop – 21st June 2023

In-person on-site at RAL – 20 attendees

JASMIN User Conference 2023 – 1st – 2nd November 2023

In-person at Harwell – 40 attendees from across JASMIN communities

JASMIN Beginners' workshop – 8 November 2023

Virtual – 10 attendees from AI4ER (Artificial Intelligence for Environmental Risk) Centre for Doctoral Training

Communicating Climate Uncertainty Workshop – 30th November 2023

Virtual – 180 people registered – Organised with ClimateEurope2

NCEO Induction day – 13 December 2023

RAL Site – 19 new NCEO staff attendees – introduction to NCEO, RAL Space and CEDA/JASMIN, including R100 and JASMIN tours

Centre for Ecology and Hydrology Visit & Webinar – 6th February 2024

Hosted in-person at RAL – 11 visitors from CEH
JASMIN CEH Webinar– 44 attendees

JASMIN Group Workspace Managers Webinar – 8th February 2024

Virtual – 42 JASMIN GWS Manager attendees

Introduction to Scientific Computing course

Module 1 (virtual) – 14 attendees – Introduction to the bash shell (Unix/Linux), 30th October 2023
Module 2 (Leeds) – 12 attendees – Introduction to Python Programming (includes Introduction to software version control with Git and GitHub) 13th – 15th November 2023
Module 3 (Leeds) – 18 attendees – Python: Working with Data, 2.5 days 15th – 17th November 2023

Providing JASMIN Training Accounts & Event Support

NCAS Climate Modelling Summer School
– 25 attendees – September 2023
NERC CLASS (Climate Linked Atlantic Sector Science) workshop – 7 organisers + 25 attendees – 29th February – 1st March 2024

Overall
we provided
training to over
450
people this year

JASMIN

